

ANALYSIS OF THE EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF RISK
FACTORS FOR MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Abstract

This article provides a systematic analysis of the epidemiological description of the factors of myocardial infarction, analysis of the literature on its current state and priority aspects.

The results obtained by them were compared and conclusions were drawn on the basis of a systematic analysis.

Key words: dyslipidemia, myocardial infarction, stroke, medicine, population, cholesterol, cholesterolemia.

Today, myocardial infarction and methods of its treatment are considered one of the urgent problems.

Throughout the world, dyslipidemia (hypercholesterolemia - HChS and hypertriglyceridemia - HTG) is considered a risk factor for coronary artery disease, including myocardial infarction, known to all medical professionals who have worked and are working in this field.

Therefore, it is important to study its causes, risk factors and prevalence at the population level.

Based on a review of the literature, we learned that DLP is observed in the population of Azerbaijan with a high prevalence.

Practically the same as the GCS is typical for GTG with a propagation frequency at high frequencies. In the studies mentioned, it is recommended to carefully study the reasons for this.

Modern research has confirmed this. Creation and implementation of preventive technologies (primary prevention, secondary and tertiary prevention) is crucial in solving the problem of MI. Because the main role in the occurrence, development and complication of the disease is played by two groups of risk factors (“the force” that ensures the success or failure of treatment):

1) factors that are constantly encountered in a person’s life: stress, physical inactivity, smoking, alcohol abuse, drug addiction, toxic addiction, malnutrition, Internet addiction, drug addiction, mental overeating, low financial condition, low level of cultural education, uncontrolled drug use (arbitrary treatment ;

2) factors affecting the collective group: unfavorable environmental conditions (air, water, soil, background radiation), high risk of infectious diseases, poor quality of food products, unsatisfactory work of medical workers, low level of material well-being - disasters of the population, natural and man-made disasters.

HOW. Shastin et al. (2022) studying the characteristics of primary morbidity (CD) of AMI in the Russian population of working age, confirmed the following: the highest average long-term level of CD (O’KIDBK) from acute myocardial infarction in the Oryol region (15300/0000), minimum O’KIDBK-Moscow (39.00/0000) confirmed. BC from CHI decreased by 9.8% in Russia in 2020, with a decrease in BC (from CHI) in 11 out of 18 regions. These results are important for public health management and, according to the conclusions of most studies, it would be appropriate if such studies were carried out regularly in different populations and in different countries and geographic areas.

S.A. Shalnova et al. . (2022) studied the prevalence of MI in the regions of Russia and assessed its contribution to cardiovascular events.

The study included a representative population aged 25-64 from 11 regions of the Russian Federation.

The prevalence of MI among the population in the regions of Russia was 2.9%, among men - 5.2%, among women - 1.5%, its increase with age was

confirmed. Men with a history of MI were more likely to receive static (39.0%) and beta-blockers (25.6%) than women (29.3% and 27.1%, respectively). MI is associated with major risk factors such as smoking, hypertension, tachycardia, hypertriglyceridemia, and hyperglycemia. The authors concluded that the presence of these risk factors indicates a lack of primary prevention of the disease and that the strengthening of preventive measures (aimed at eliminating CW) leads to a decrease in the risk of recurrent myocardial infarction and cardiovascular death.

Their association with MI, according to the study and ESSE-RF results
Epidemiological characteristics of myocardial infarction factors

Epidemiological indicators	Men (p = 4948); MI- 259.5.2%	Women (p = 8498); MI-259.1.5%
Average age, years	56.4 ±5.7	58.8±3.5
≥ 50 ёш, n%	87.6	94.6
Below average data, n%	6.6	11.6
Average data level is low, p%	55.6	60.5
Above average data, n%	37.8	27.9
Smoking population, p%	37.1	7.8
Low-income population, n%	20.8	23.3
Incomes of the population, n%	61.4	71.3
Population with high incomes, n%	17.8	5.4
Alcohol abuse, p%	1.9	1.6
AG, p%	82.2	87.6
Diabetes mellitus, p%	14.3	31.0
PZLP ChS, mmol/l	3.3 ±1.2	3.7±1.1
YUZLP HS, mmol/l	1.2±0.3	1.4±0.3
TG, mmol/l	1.4(1.1;2.0)	1.5(1.0;2.1)
Total cholesterol, mmol/l	5.2±1.5	5.8±1.4
Creatinine, mmol/l	5.5(5.0;6.2)	5.6(5.0;6.7)
GARDEN, mm. see column	142.2±22.0	150.8±25.2

DBP, mm see column	86.5±13.4	86.8±12.1
HIGH, 1 min/amount	70.9±11.0	75.1±11.4
OTV, kg / m ²	29.2±4.2	31.9±7.9
QT, cm	98.2±12.1	96.1±14.3
Balls - ml / min / 1.73 m ²	103.4	89.3
General 8 mm, p%	23.9	8.5
8mm, n% of YUQK	10.4	3.1
MI, n%	9.7	7
Total deviation point, p%	19.7	8.5

Similar epidemiological studies were carried out by other studies (only in non-CIS countries).

In particular, Virani SS et al (2021) Hashim MJ et al. (2016) and Nowbar AN et al. (2019) confirm that CVD/MI is the leading cause of death and disability among complications of cardiovascular disease and is a global public health problem worldwide.

Khan M.A. et al. According to (2020), the burden of CKD/MI increases in parallel with the increase in life expectancy. The main reason for the increase in MI in the population is the epidemic growth of CKD, which is also confirmed by these authors.

MI is becoming increasingly problematic and/or relevant due to the epidemic burden of MI. In recent years, HCV has created an unacceptable epidemiological situation with the following aspects: 1) according to the Global Burden Study (2020), 126 million people (1.72% of the world's population) are infected with HCV; 2) In Europe, the prevalence of IUDs is 3,547 per 100,000 people, in the USA - 2,929, in Russia - 4,198 per 100,000 people.

Such conclusions will, of course, vary by region, population, or country.

The data obtained in the epidemiological study "ESSE-RF-prospective" conducted in Russia show that the prevalence of MI in this country is significantly

higher than in other countries, even in the absence of this disease, it is mainly formed under the influence of biological and modifiable risk factors .

So, the table shows that the elimination of CW with the timely use of primary prevention means, that is, maintaining primary prevention at close range without "breaking away from the population", creates a chance to save a person's health from myocardial infarction, or give a chance - give the patient a chance to live in life is sharply reduced.

The control of the level of atherogenic blood lipids among these CWs is especially important in the implementation of strategies for effective primary and secondary prevention of coronary artery disease/MI.

Reduction of atherogenic lipids to target levels is considered a key factor in the prevention of CHD/MI.

For this purpose, statins are mainly used, but in contrast to them, the achievement of lipid levels to a normal level is observed in practice only from 12% to 35%.

The reasons for such results are the inactivity of doctors in enhancing lipid-lowering therapy, insufficient fulfillment of their duties by patients, often they have to leave cases of familial hypercholesterolemia undiagnosed.

The attitude of physicians towards MI also plays an important role in identifying and solving its problems.

In recent years, the number of studies devoted to this scientific topic has increased dramatically.

A. A. Gerasimov and R. B. Polibinlar (2019) examined 172 respondents using an anonymous survey. The questionnaire consisted of 37 questions, and through them the attitude of doctors to clinical recommendations (CT) was determined. 44.2% of physicians are familiar with proven medical principles and 52.3% with clinical epidemiology). Dissatisfaction with existing clinical guidelines was confirmed by 41.9% of physicians. 40.7% of respondents knew the criteria for

diagnosing recurrent MI, and 26.7% reported that they knew the recommendations for cardiovascular prevention and cardiac rehabilitation. Only 38.4% of physicians positively assessed the expediency of lifelong prescription of drugs to patients with MI, and only 16.3% of the surveyed physicians rated as effective (leading to the prevention of MI recurrence) methods aimed at eliminating modifiable risk factors.

Based on this, the authors conclude that doctors use the principles of proven medicine and clinical epidemiology without sufficient understanding of their concepts. From them it can be concluded that MI is still considered a disease that causes the most dangerous consequences of coronary heart disease, and is recognized as such.

References

1. Asfandiyarova N.S. Multiple chronic pain / N.S. Asfandiyarova // Clinical gerontology. - 2018. - V. 24, No. 3-4. -WITH. 58-64.
2. Beilina, N.I. Comorbidity of patients in a therapeutic hospital / N.I. Beilina, A.O. Pozdnyak // Practical medicine. -2018. - No. 9. - S. 74-77.
- 3 . Mamasaliev , N.S. Acute coronary syndrome in Uzbekistan: features of diagnosis, treatment and prevention, treatment and prevention, treatment and registration in Andijan and comparison with data from other countries / N.S. Mamasaliev ,
4. M.A. Kachkovsky , Z.N. Mamasaliev [and others] // Bulletin of the Medical Institute " Reaviz ": rehabilitation, doctor and health. -2018.-T. 35, No. 5.- S.32-40.